

D5.1 Website

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

DECO	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach
Dx.x	Deliverable number
PMG	Project Management Group
PC	Project Coordinator

1 Introduction

The ICEBERG project has a twofold aim:

- to produce a deeper understanding of pollution and its impacts on ecosystems and communities in the Arctic in combination with climate-induced stressors
- to create strategies for enhancing community-led resilience and adaptation, as well as pollution-control governance and policy recommendations

In addition, the project aims to develop new knowledge and tools for ethical and inclusive citizen science practices.

A visual identity strengthens the identity of the project and it will be a basis for visual DECO materials. A project website is a home base for project communications to main target groups, hosting general information, news and events, blogs, deliverables, scientific publications, policy briefs and other project related publications. It also presents the project's key messages and has a crucial role in promoting the project as well as disseminating the project's results. The project website supports the DECO objectives defined in the D5.2 DECO strategy.

The project website was published in M3. Before the final project website is published, a temporary one-pager has been used to provide the basic information about the project, from the end of M1 onwards. The website URL is <https://arcticeberg.eu>.

ICEBERG project's website will be updated regularly and developed further as needed. The website is maintained and updated by KASKAS, but all the project partners contribute by producing content and suggesting options to the website.

The visual identity strengthens the identity of the project and it will be a basis for visual DECO materials. Elements of the visual identity are also described and displayed in this document.

2 Visual identity

The logo for the ICEBERG project (Figure 1) was designed to visually convey the project's core themes: human connection and the importance of community observation and monitoring (represented by the eye) and the geographical focus on the Arctic Ocean (depicted through the iceberg and sea waves). Comprising two components, the logo features the eye integrated into the letter "C" and the project acronym as the text element. A full name version of the logo is also available.

Innovative Community Engagement for Building
Effective Resilience and Arctic Ocean Pollution-control
Governance in the Context of Climate Change

QUICK GUIDELINES FOR LOGO

Colour logo (primary)

SAFE AREA

Always take safe area into account when using the logo. Do not place any graphical elements or text inside the safe area. Safe area is the height of alphabet I of the logo.

Black logo for no-colour medias and lighter backgrounds

White logo is for dark backgrounds

Logo and image background (contrast must be sufficient)

Figure 1. The logo of the ICEBERG project

ICEBERG's visual elements include a colour palette, fonts and photography style (Figure 2). The main colours are blue and green in different shades. Colours have been designed with accessibility in mind. Typography of the ICEBERG project is accessible and fonts contain the glyphs used in Iceland and Greenland languages.

Primary colours

Dark Blue
 RGB 0, 43, 119
 CMYK 100, 80, 0, 0
 PMS 2747 C
 HEX #002b77

Purple
 RGB 117, 139, 255
 CMYK 60, 44, 0, 0
 PMS 2715 C
 HEX #758BFF

Light Blue
 RGB 217, 217, 255
 CMYK 20, 17, 0, 0
 PMS 2635 C
 HEX #d9d9ff

Neutral colors

White
 RGB 255, 255, 255
 CMYK 0, 0, 0, 0
 HEX #ffffff

Light grey (Background)
 RGB 247, 247, 247
 CMYK 0, 0, 0, 5
 HEX #f7f7f7

Additional colors

Dark Green
 RGB 0, 84, 86
 CMYK 90, 0, 45, 70
 PMS 7722 C
 HEX #005456

Green
 RGB 78, 197, 154
 CMYK 43, 0, 28, 0
 PMS 3385 C
 HEX #4ec59a

Light Green
 RGB 226, 247, 227
 CMYK 19, 0, 20, 0
 PMS 2253 C
 HEX #e2f7e3

Orange (Highlight colour)
 RGB 255, 112, 74
 CMYK 0, 70, 100, 0
 PMS 165 C
 HEX #ff704a

Black (Text)
 RGB 25, 25, 25
 CMYK 0, 0, 0, 95
 PMS BLACK 6 C
 HEX #191919

Figure 2. Visual elements: colours

Inter

Light

Regular

Medium

SemiBold

Bold

Inter

Used for headlines,
subheadlines and body text.

Pitch Sans

Bold

Pitch Sans

Used for smaller text
and headlines.

Figure 3. Visual elements: typography

ICEBERG is illustrated through photographs taken in Iceland, Svalbard and Greenland (Kalaallit Nunaat) . Photographs bring an approachable touch to the visual identity. The image style consists of elements of the local landscape or natural surroundings combined with a detail of human or natural aspects. This way, ICEBERG's visual representation involves an interplay between zooming-in and zooming-out that captures both the intricate details of human or natural elements and the wider context of surrounding landscapes.

Figure 4. Visual elements: photographs

3 Website concept

The project website was published in M3. The website has language versions in English, Kalaallisut (Greenlandic) and Icelandic. Before the final project website is published, a temporary one-pager has been used to provide basic information about the project, from the end of M1 onwards.

The project website is targeted at all the target groups, stakeholders and rights holders who are interested in ICEBERG and want to find out more about the project. The website offers information on the project's:

- goals, timeline, and outputs
- research questions and topics
- partners
- case studies
- contact information and
- funding

On the website, the project will publish and link:

- frameworks, models and data created in the project
- latest scientific articles, policy briefs, deliverables, media coverage and presentations which are interesting to target groups, stakeholders and rights holders
- blog posts (also including news and events)
- links to the project's social media channels and a newsletter subscription form

The website URL is <https://arcticeberg.eu>. The website is maintained and updated by KASKAS.

3.1 Development phases

Phase 1: Planning and benchmarking

The development process of the website started at the very beginning of the project. At this stage, the objectives for the website were defined and discussed. Also, other project websites were benchmarked.

Phase 2: Onepager

The onepager website was published in M3 to act as a replacement website while the actual website was in production. The onepager included a brief description of the project, a list of partners and contact information.

Phase 3: Website structure and content production

The website structure was created by KASKAS in M1-M2. The structure included description and the function of each section of the website. The texts for the website were produced by KASKAS in M2 at the same time with the DECO strategy (D5.2) process. The Project Coordinator was consulted during the process.

Phase 4: Layout

The layout of the website was designed by KASKAS during M2 after the content of the website was created. The layout was designed using the visual identity of the project.

Phase 5: Technical design

The website was technically built by the digital design agency Bildy in M3. Bildy was chosen from four service providers based on the "best value for money" principle.

Phase 6: Testing and publishing

The website was tested by KASKAS in M3. The finalized website was published in M3.

4 Website structure

4.1 Front page

The front page (Figure 5) displays project’s key messages and enables a possibility to manually highlight current and relevant publications to promote the impact of the project. The front page also lists latest events, blog posts and news under the heading, “Recent”, and it contains a map of the project’s field study sites. At the foot of the page is a link to subscribe to the newsletter and contact information of the project. This “footer” is also on each subpage of the website.

Figure 5. Front page

4.2 Project

The “Project” (Figure 6) section contains a brief description and overview of the project’s general information such as themes, contents and goals. It has also two subsections to describe the challenges that the project aims to tackle and project’s goals. In addition, this section lists the partners of the project consortium.

Figure 6. Project

4.3 Case study sites

The section "Case study sites" (Figure 7) provides an overview of the three case study locations of the project. The section provides a more detailed description on each case study site and a visual map of the locations. In addition, the section contains a link to the interactive open-source platform for citizen participation.

Figure 7. Case study sites

4.4 Current topics

The “Current topics” (Figure 8) section includes all the events, news and blog posts created within the project. Website users can filter content by different categories using the search function.

Figure 8. Current topics

4.5 Publications

The “Publications” (Figure 9) section gathers public outputs created during the project. Here, website users will find links to project deliverables and other publications such as scientific publications and policy briefs. The search function helps users to find different types of outputs.

Figure 9. Publications